

THE IMPORTANCE OF TEACHING VOCABULARY

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Annotation: The article provides information about how importance of vocabulary in learning and teaching English and methodical organization. Methodical organization of vocabulary teaching depends on what kind of speech activity it is intended to activate. The article is also pay attention to material for speech, the lexicon of speech, lexical side of the written and lexical side of listening.

Key words: speech, lexical side of listening, The lexicon of speech, lexical side of the written, lexicology, orthography, transcription, synonym, antonyms, homonym.

Teaching vocabulary is the basis of language teaching. Vocabulary is a collection of learned words and phrases. It is not possible to learn and to become the master of speech activities without mastering the vocabulary. It is used as material for speech activities. Material for speech is very important. There is no speech without the material. You can learn English by listening to the English speech and understanding the meaning of the words that you have already learnt. If the student does not know the words or does not know the meaning of the words, the information will remain unclear and the meaning of the speech will remain unclear. When working on the lexical side of listening comprehension, the ability of the listening to and recognize it is widely used, because listening to and recognizing the lexicon also has its own character and difficulty. The lexicon of speech has its own peculiarities. A student and a pupil cannot speak unless they know about it, even they knew about the lexicon of speech they should be able to put it in its place. The lexical side of reading also makes it difficult to communicate. The student can receive all information from reading by looking every single word. In order to understand their meaning and content, it is necessary to know and understand words beforehand. There is also a need to work on the lexical side of the written statement. The learners must be able to write, pronounce, and read the word so that they can write meaningful and accurate information.

To know a language means to master its structure and words. Thus, vocabulary is one of the aspects of the language to be taught in school. The problem is what words and idioms pupils should retain. It is evident that the number of words should be limited because pupils here only 2-4 periods a week; the size of the group is not small enough to provide each pupil with practice in speaking; schools are not yet

equipped with special laboratories for individual language learning. The number of words pupils should acquire in school depends wholly on the syllabus requirements.

In teaching vocabulary practical needs both structural words and content words are of great importance. That is why they are included in the vocabulary minimum. The selection of the vocabulary although important is not the teacher’s chief concern. It is only the “what” of teaching and is usually prescribed for him by textbooks and studyguides he uses. The teacher’s concern is “how” to get his pupils to assimilate the vocabulary (prescribed) prescribed. This is a difficult problem and it is still in the process of being solved. It is generally known that school leavers’ vocabulary is poor. They have trouble with hearing, speaking, reading and writing. One of the reasons is poor teaching of vocabulary. Learning the words of a foreign language is not an easy business since every word has its form, meaning, and usage and each of these aspects of the word may have

its difficulties. Indeed, some words are difficult in form (daughter, busy, woman, women) and easy in usage; other words are easy in form (enter, get, happen) and difficult in usage. The analysis of the words within the foreign language allows us to distinguish the following groups of words: concrete, abstract and structural.

Words denoting concrete things (book, street, sky), action (walk, dance, read), and qualities (long, big, good) are easier to learn than words denoting abstract notions (world, home, believe, promise, honest). Structural words are the most difficult for Russian – speaking pupils. Words are elements of the language used in the act of communication. There are some rules for the teacher in teaching vocabulary.

Rule 1: While teaching pupils vocabulary, introduce words in sentence patterns in different situations of intercourse. Present the words in keeping with the structures to the taught. Information is composed of 2 kinds of elements: simple (words) and complicated (sentences).

Rule 2: Present the word as an element, i.e., in a sentence pattern first. Then fix it in the pupils’ memory through different exercises in sentence patterns and phrase patterns.

Rule 3: While introducing a word pronounce it yourself in a context, ask pupils to pronounce it both individually and in unison in a context, too.

Rule 4: In teaching words it is necessary to establish a memory bond between a new word and those already covered.

For instance: see – sea; too – two; one – won (in pronunciation); answer – reply; answer – ask; small – little (in meaning); bought – brought; caught – taught; night – right (in spelling); to fight smb. – боротьсяпротивкого-либо; to doubt smth. – сомневатьсявчем-либо; to mention smth – упоминатьо чем-либо (similar word combination).

Used literatures:

1. Ingliz tili o'quv fani bo'yicha umumiy o'rta ta'lim maktablari uchun dastur. T. 1999 y.
2. J.J. Djalolov O'rta maktabda ingliz tili o'qitish metodikasi. Toshkent, O'qituvchi nashriyoti 1997 yil.
3. J.J. Jalolov, G.T. Makhkamova, Sh.S. Ashurov English Language Teaching Methodology (theory and practice).- T.: "Fan va texnologiya", 2015

